

ABSORBTING ENGLISH EXPRESSIONS THAT USED IN THE PADDINGTON

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Abstract. Nowadays learning languages has become more important and the use of media in English teaching and learning has received much attention from educators and foreign language educators. Learning a new language not only develops individual intelligence, but also it gives learners, permission to enter and gets learners near to another culture as well as beneficial in terms of increasing students' cultural awareness, as well as change their behavior. There are many methods to increase students' English skills, such as listening to the music, podcast, reading a lot of article, watching movies, writing story etc. The study's results indicated that language learners believed that movies are authentic sources of language learning and can be used effectively to improve language skills including speaking, listening, reading, vocabulary, and writing. Through movie the students will feel excited and did not get bored easily especially watch their favorite movies. This paper aims to propose the use of movies at high school by discussing English Expressions with movie named, "Paddington" which gained first place from students favorite list at senior high school for EFL learner.

Key words: culture, excited, idiom, vocabulary, expressions.

INTRODUCTION

Learning a new language not only develops individual intelligence, but also it gives learners, permission to enter and gets learners near to another culture and prepares them with the essential skills to succeed and change their behavior in a rapidly changing world (Chan, Deborah, 1999) [1, p.4]. When you think of learning, especially a second language, reading language books, playing recordings of lessons, and attending class with a language coach often comes to mind. However, understanding new vocabularies and phrases are always essential, and the practice is vital way of succeeding those. The students' listening and comprehension skills will be practiced while watching movies, besides, putting on subtitles is the best chance to practice their English reading skills. Movies are a part of visual literacy and "movies are an enjoyable source of entertainment and language acquisition". Using movies in the classrooms or as an outside school activity can support motivation of the learners, because of their playful component, and they can be used as task activities to give an ideal environment for learning, as well as encouraging participation and interaction among students (Chan & Herrero, 2010).

This paper is aimed at providing some key specifics as to why watching movies , especially Paddington, is good for your English language journey. This strategy of using English movies for English expressions commonly used in the Paddington movie, and about their benefit. Therefore, this paper also states the benefits of using English movie as an attractive teaching and learning strategy.

English Expressions Commonly Used in the Paddington [2].

English is not a complicated language. However, certain expressions are used, often in informal and conversational settings, that can't be learned in formal schooling or a language coach. These expressions should not be taken literally and can only be appreciated through constant practice of the language. Since the Paddington shows a light and fun on life, it is an excellent venue to know common English expressions. Here are some of the most used English expressions in the movie, what they mean, and how they can be used in real life.

•1. "Get one's ticket punched"

May be confused for: hit one's ticket.

What it actually means: To die; to be killed. (Literally, to be cancelled).

How it was used:

In 01:18, When the explorer found undiscovered species of bears .

Explorer: *And finally, deep in the undergrowth, I spot something extraordinary. An undiscovered species of bear. Time to collect a specimen for the museum. I thought my time was up, my ticket was punched.*

How you can use it in real life:

Poor Chuck got his ticket punched while he was waiting for a bus.

Tom had his ticket punched by a rival gang member.

Trotsky became a liability, so Stalin had his ticket punched.

It's a raw deal to have one's ticket punched the day before Christmas.

Watch out there, or you'll get your ticket punched.

• 2. "Batten down the hatches"

May be confused for: to fasten something by fixing pieces of wood onto it.

What it actually means: to prepare for a difficult situation.

How it was used:

In 20:51, When Mrs. Bird felt storm in her knees.

Mrs. Bird: *Batten down the hatches, young. There will be a storm tonight.*

Mrs. Brown: *The radio said it was clearing up.*

Mrs. Bird: *Radio! I feel it in my knees. My knees never lie.*

How you can use it in real life:

When you're coming down with flu all you can do is batten down the hatches and wait for it to pass.

Many firms are battening down the hatches and preparing to ride out the storm.

There's a tornado coming—batten down the hatches!

My mother-in-law is coming to town this weekend, so I better batten down the hatches.

After months of fears about the economy, consumers are ready to batten down the hatches.

• 3. "Pull someone's leg"

May be confused for: to move someone's leg towards yourself.

What it actually means: to try to persuade someone to believe something that is not true, as a joke.

How it was used:

In 37:18, When Mr. Gruber found marmalade in Paddington's hat.

Mr. Gruber: *Unusual color. But it is hard to say how much... Marmalade?*

Paddington: *My uncle always kept a marmalade sandwich in his hat in case of emergency.*

Mr. Gruber: *You are pulling my legs off. What a splendid idea.*

How you can use it in real life:

Is it really your car or are you pulling my leg?

I panicked when he said the test was tomorrow, but then I realized he was just pulling my leg.

Stop pulling my leg – you didn't have lunch with Bono!

I haven't won, have I? You are pulling my leg.

Did Ronnie really call or are you just pulling my leg?

- 4. "Mind (out)!"

May be confused for: to be annoyed or worried by something.

What it actually means: used to tell someone to move or be careful, or to warn someone of danger.

How it was used:

In 35:12, It was used by cyclist, When Paddington was crossing the road.

Paddington: *Oh, wait a minute. The gentleman dropped his wallet.*

Cyclist: *Mind out!*

How you can use it in real life:

Mind out! We're coming through with the stretcher.

Mind out! There's a car coming.

"Hey, mind!" he said when she trod on his foot.

I was known to be no trouble and I suppose so near the end of my stretch they didn't think to mind out for me.

Mind out -- there's a snowball coming towards you!

- 5. "Take charge"

May be confused for: to take opportunity.

What it actually means: to accept responsibility for something and have control over it.

How it was used:

In 41:55, when Mr. and Mrs. Brown were arguing about Paddington.

Mr Brown: *Stop. We have done quite enough for this bear. I am taking charge! Paddington is a danger to this family.*

How you can use it in real life:

She took charge of the project and made sure it was finished on time.

The manager had to take charge after the project failed to meet its initial deadline.

Mary's going to take charge of the desk for the evening.

I was unexpectedly asked to take charge of their children when they passed away.

When the new manager took charge, things really began to happen.

CONCLUSION

Movie is one of audio-visual media that can be used by English teachers to improve student's English skills [3]. There are some advantages of using Paddington in English teaching, such as movies can keep student's interest in learning English, movies can improve student's listening skill, can improve student's speaking skill, Writing skill, can improve student's pronunciation, grammar, and can boost student's vocabulary with commonly used expressions . Moreover, using Paddington to teach English is fun and everyone loves watching movies strengthens the teacher's confidence to use English movies as an attractive strategy to teach English as a Foreign Language to senior high school student.

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